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Optimization of Dosimetry in Radiotherapy Using Machine Learning to Personalize
Treatments in Patients with Cancer

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*TO MY MOM, THE STRONGEST PERSON I KNOW AND WHO
TAUGHT ME TO NEVER GIVE UP*

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, machine learning systems have achieved impressive performances comparable to and even superior to human level in various tasks. However, these advances have relied heavily on vast amounts of data, such as large volumes of labeled data or continuous evaluations in controlled environments. In contrast, human learning is predominantly unsupervised, guided by observation and interaction with the environment. Emulating this type of learning in machines constitutes a crucial challenge to achieve general artificial intelligence. This context has led to the incorporation of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) in the field of radiotherapy, where these tools can significantly improve diagnostic accuracy and the efficiency of clinical processes, marking a milestone in cancer treatment.

Radiotherapy fundamentally depends on precise dosimetric planning, a process that seeks to maximize the dose delivered and prescribed to the tumor while minimizing the exposure of healthy tissues. Automated treatment planning (ATP) has emerged as an innovative solution to improve the quality and consistency of radiotherapy plans, while reducing the workload of clinical staff. Tools such as RapidPlan have demonstrated that automation based on prior knowledge allows for the generation of personalized treatment plans by analyzing complex data patterns. Machine learning models, such as convolutional neural networks (CNN), stand out for their ability to optimize dose distributions, achieving effective tumor irradiation with less affectation to organs at risk (OARs). On this basis, the present project seeks to contribute to the refinement of the standard radiotherapy planning process by applying advanced methodologies.

The project combines machine learning with Monte Carlo simulations to optimize radiotherapy treatments, offering a comprehensive and novel approach. Specifically, convolutional neural networks will analyze clinical imaging data, like a computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET) scans and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), to identify tumor regions and organs at risk. Monte Carlo simulations will complement this analysis by generating probabilistic radiation dose distributions, allowing treatment parameters to be adjusted to maximize irradiation to the tumor and minimize adverse effects on healthy tissues. This hybrid system not only improves the efficiency and precision of radiotherapy, but also offers a scalable and adaptable approach, with potential applications in diverse and challenging clinical settings.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

Radiotherapy represents one of the most effective therapeutic modalities for the treatment of cancer, by destroying malignant cells through the precise application of ionizing radiation. This process seeks to maximize the dose to the tumor while minimizing the exposure of surrounding healthy tissues. However, traditional dosimetric planning is a manual and complex process that relies heavily on the experience of clinical staff. This generates variability in results and extends planning times, affecting the efficiency of the health system and treatment start times for patients.

The advent of deep learning has significantly transformed various areas of medicine, particularly in radiotherapy. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) have proven to be highly effective tools for segmenting medical images and predicting three-dimensional dose distributions. For example, approaches such as systems based on U-Net architectures have made it possible to advance the automation of radiotherapy planning by analyzing complex clinical data with high accuracy. In parallel, Monte Carlo simulations have established themselves as a standard in dose distribution modelling, offering a unique ability to assess dosimetric parameters under realistic conditions. This methodological combination offers significant potential to optimise radiotherapy treatments, improving both the accuracy and consistency of treatment plans.

This project aspires to integrate these two advanced technologies – deep learning and Monte Carlo simulations – to address the limitations inherent in traditional dosimetric planning approaches. Monte Carlo simulations will be performed using the GEANT4 platform, known for its ability to model the precise interaction of radiation with human tissues and provide detailed probabilistic dose distributions. This methodology will allow complex scenarios to be explored and treatment parameters to be dynamically adjusted to obtain more effective results.

In addition, the development of the machine learning system will be carried out using Python, a programming language widely adopted in the scientific community for its flexibility and ability to handle large volumes of data. Tools such as TensorFlow and Keras will be used to implement and train convolutional neural networks, focused on accurate organ segmentation and dose distribution

prediction. The combination of these techniques will allow for detailed and robust analysis of dosimetric behavior, improving the customization of treatment plans. The implementation of this system aims not only to improve current standards in radiotherapy, but also to demonstrate the viability of scalable and adaptable solutions that can be integrated into various clinical settings.

1.2 Problem Statement

Radiotherapy is a fundamental treatment for cancer, but its success depends on accurate and efficient dosimetric planning. Current planning methods often involve labor-intensive manual adjustments or limited automation, which can lead to variability in treatment quality and inefficiencies in clinical workflows. Traditional approaches to dose calculation, such as Monte Carlo simulations, are known for their accuracy, but are computationally expensive and time-consuming, posing challenges for real-time clinical applications (Neph et al. 2019). While recent advances in machine learning, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have shown promise in automating and accelerating dose prediction, existing models still face limitations in handling complex dose distributions and patient-specific anatomical variability (Peng et al. 2019).

This thesis addresses these challenges by proposing a hybrid dosimetric optimization system that integrates the probabilistic accuracy of Monte Carlo simulations with the computational efficiency of CNNs. By leveraging Monte Carlo methods to model dose distributions and CNNs to process patient imaging data, the system aims to automate and refine dosimetry planning with increased accuracy and consistency. This hybrid approach builds on previous research that demonstrated the potential of CNNs to accelerate Monte Carlo simulations and produce high-quality dose predictions (Neph et al. 2019; Peng et al. 2019). The proposed system aims to optimize radiotherapy treatments by accurately delivering radiation to tumors and minimizing exposure to healthy tissues at risk, while eliminating most human error factor, thereby improving clinical outcomes and treatment planning efficiency.

1.3 Research Questions

- How can a hybrid system that integrates Monte Carlo simulations and convolutional neural networks (CNN) optimize dosimetry plans in radiotherapy?
- How can Monte Carlo simulations complement CNN predictions to improve dose accuracy and minimize exposure to organs at risk?
- What performance metrics best assess the efficacy of the hybrid system compared to traditional planning methods?
- What are the computational and integration challenges for implementing the hybrid system in real-world clinical workflows and how can they be addressed?

1.4 Thesis Objectives

- Develop a hybrid dosimetric optimization system that combines Monte Carlo simulations and convolutional neural networks (CNN), thus improving radiotherapy dosimetric planning.
- Identify the most important features of clinical data and images (CT/PET/MRI) to feed the CNN model and predict optimal dose distributions.
- Design, implement and train a convolutional neural network model capable of analyzing clinical imaging data and generating initial dose distribution predictions.
- Integrate the CNN model predictions with Monte Carlo simulations to refine dosimetric parameters, ensuring maximum irradiation to the tumor and minimizing damage to healthy tissues.
- Evaluate the efficiency of the hybrid system using metrics such as the Dice Similarity Coefficient, Conformity Index and Homogeneity Index, comparing it with traditional methods and certified software.

Chapter 2: Theoretical Background

To understand and develop it, we have to apply concepts and theory from different fields, from physics (interaction of radiation with matter), to programming (Machine Learning) and more practical topics (Medicine/Radiotherapy). To develop this project, we must understand how to use and train a neural network (Programming), what libraries to use, how to train the capabilities and know the basics of physics and mathematics behind radiotherapy, since this must be converted into computer language. It is important to know what the Monte Carlo method is, which will help us with the probability distribution of doses for radiotherapy plans (Figure 2.0.1), (Allison, K. Amako, JEA Apostolakis, et al. 2006; Allison, K. Amako, John Apostolakis, et al. 2016; Agostinelli et al. 2003). we can see our framework to develop this project plus Visual Studio Code using C++ and Python language.

Figure 2.0.1: Frame Work System

2.1 Introduction to Dosimetric Planning in Radiotherapy

Ionizing radiation used as external beam radiotherapy, brachytherapy and targeted radionuclide therapy is one of the most effective treatment modalities in patients with tumours. Tumours are more prone to radiation damage than normal tissues and this is enhanced by the use of fractionated treatment, which preferentially spares normal tissue by allowing recovery from radiation damage between fractions of radiotherapy (RT). The magnitude of the differential biological effect on tumour and normal tissue is described as the therapeutic ratio, and is determined by the radioresponse of tumours relative to the risk of critical dose-limiting damage to the system. RT for some malignant tumours, (e.g. Germinoma), is the mainstay curative treatment. Excellent disease control after conservative surgery and radiotherapy in benign tumours such as optic nerve/chiasm glioma, pituitary adenoma and craniopharyngioma has established RT as an essential component of treatment. In high-grade gliomas, RT prolongs survival beyond that seen with any other treatment modality. RT is also an effective palliative treatment in patients with severe metastases.

2.1.1 Dosimetric planning

Dosimetric planning is a critical component of radiation therapy, ensuring that patients receive an optimal balance between delivering a dose sufficient to eradicate cancerous tumors and minimizing exposure to surrounding healthy tissues. The goal of this process is to maximize the therapeutic ratio, which represents the effectiveness of tumor control relative to the potential for complications in normal tissues. Traditional dosimetric planning involves manual or semi-automated processes, which are labor-intensive and highly dependent on the experience of clinical professionals, high dose delivery accuracy is a long-standing requirement in radiotherapy treatments (Brahme, Chavaudra, and Landberg 1988; Radiological Units (ICRU) 1976). To achieve such accuracy, uncertainties at all stages of the radiotherapy process, from simulation and planning to treatment delivery, must be reduced as much as possible (Mijnheer, Battermann, and Wambersie 1987). Central to this is the need to know and understand the magnitude of potential errors associated with each stage of the process. The introduction of increasingly complex treatment techniques and with them the possibility of delivering higher doses in radiotherapy treatments has reinforced the requirement for accuracy in dose calculation algorithms. Historically, one of the most serious weaknesses in

treatment planning systems has been their ability to accurately predict doses in the presence of inhomogeneities, in particular through poor consideration of electron transport (Engelsman et al. 2001; Shahine, Al-Ghazi, and El-Khatib 1999).

Inaccuracies in dose calculation lead to systematic errors in radiotherapy treatments and are therefore of particular importance (Radiological Units (ICRU) 1987). The Anisotropic Analytical Algorithm (AAA) is the most recent photon dose calculation algorithm implemented in the Eclipse treatment planning system (Varian Medical Systems, Palo Alto, CA, USA). Developed by Ulmer et al. (Ulmer and Harder 1996; Ulmer and Kaissl 1995), it is a convolution superposition model that uses pre-computed treatment unit-specific parameters together with beam data measured at end-user linear accelerators to model clinical treatment beams. Inhomogeneity correction is implemented through anisotropic scaling of the photon and electron scattering kernels, according to the electron density distribution of the treated medium (Ulmer, Pyyry, and Kaissl 2005). The performance of the algorithm in homogeneous media is investigated through comparison with measurements in water, initially for simple beam geometries and subsequently for more complex situations, others are made with different material and are based on the simplest and most widely used so-called phantoms. Comparisons are then usually made on a series of solid phantoms to assess the algorithm's ability to accurately predict dose in non-homogeneous media. Finally, simulated treatment plans are applied to a semi-anthropomorphic phantom to test the algorithm's overall dosimetric performance in clinically realistic situations, moving on to the simulation that we will do using datasets with real anonymized users that provide us with real images and data (which will give us doses to offer the optimization of realistic radiotherapy plans).

2.2 Machine Learning in Medical Applications

To date, research on machine learning methods for medical applications is still focused on technological issues and is primarily application-oriented. However, to answer fundamental questions and gain useful insights into the performance and behavior of machine learning methods in a medical context, it is important to improve our understanding of machine learning algorithms as well as provide mathematical justifications for their properties. Machine learning (ML) provides methods, techniques, and tools that can help solve diagnostic and prognostic problems in a variety of medical

domains. ML is being used for the analysis of the importance of clinical parameters and their combinations for prognosis, for example, prediction of disease progression, medical knowledge extraction for outcome research, therapeutic planning and support, and for general patient management. ML is also being used for data analysis, such as detection of regularities in data by appropriate handling of imperfect data, interpretation of continuous data used in the Intensive Care Unit, and intelligent alarming resulting in effective and efficient monitoring. It is argued that successful implementation of ML methods can aid the integration of computer-based systems into the healthcare environment, providing opportunities to facilitate and enhance the work of medical experts and ultimately improve the efficiency and quality of healthcare. Below, we summarize some of the main applications of ML in medicine. Medical diagnostic reasoning is a very important application area of intelligent systems (Hellebust, Jørgensen, and Hafeez 2011; Kestin, Martinez, and Guerrero 2009; Llacer, Perez, and Herrero 2022) . In this framework, expert systems and model-based schemes provide mechanisms for hypothesis generation from patient data. For example, rules are extracted from experts' knowledge to build expert systems. Unfortunately, in many cases, experts may not know, or be able to formulate, what knowledge they actually use to solve their problems. Symbolic learning techniques (e.g., inductive learning) are used to add learning and knowledge management capabilities to expert systems (Nielsen 2015). Given a set of clinical cases acting as examples, learning in intelligent systems can be achieved using ML methods that are capable of producing a systematic description of those clinical features that uniquely characterize the clinical conditions, based on this we will use a subfield that is derived from machine learning called neural networks which must be differentiated from deep learning.

2.2.1 Neural Networks

Neural networks are one of the most beautiful programming paradigms ever invented. In the conventional approach to programming, we tell the computer what to do, breaking down large problems into many small, precisely defined tasks that the computer can easily perform. In contrast, in a neural network we do not tell the computer how to solve our problem. Instead, it learns from observational data, discovering its own solution to the problem at hand. It automatically learns from the data. However, until 2006 we did not know how to train neural networks to outperform more traditional approaches, except on a few specialized problems. What changed in 2006 was the

discovery of techniques for learning so-called deep neural networks, which are now known as deep learning. They have been developed further and today deep neural networks and recognition using deep learning achieve outstanding performance on many important problems in computer vision, speech, and natural language processing. Companies such as Google, Microsoft, and Facebook are deploying them on a large scale(Nielsen 2015).

Artificial neural networks are popular machine learning techniques that simulate the learning mechanism in biological organisms. The human nervous system contains cells, called neurons. Neurons are connected to each other by axons and dendrites, and the connection regions between axons and dendrites are called synapses. The strength of synaptic connections often changes in response to external stimuli. This change is how learning occurs in living organisms(Aggarwal 2018). This biological mechanism is simulated in artificial neural networks, which contain components, computing units, that are called neurons. An artificial neural network calculates a function of the inputs by propagating the calculated values from the input neurons to the output neurons and using the weights as intermediate parameters. Learning occurs by changing the weights that connect the neurons. Just as external stimuli are necessary for learning in biological organisms, the external stimulus in artificial neural networks is provided by training data that contains examples of input-output pairs of the function to be learned. For example, training data may contain image pixel representations (input) and their annotated labels (e.g. carrot, banana) as output. These training data pairs are fed into the neural network using the input representations to make predictions about the output labels (ibid.).

2.3 Monte Carlo Method

The Monte Carlo simulation method is an essential tool for reliability and risk analysis in complex systems. This approach allows for realistic analysis by removing many of the limiting assumptions typically applied in other methods (Z. Liu, Feng, and X. e. a. Wang 2020). Monte Carlo simulation is based on the use of random sampling to obtain numerical solutions to problems that are too complex or impossible to solve analytically. By generating a large number of possible scenarios, this method provides a deep understanding of how uncertainties and variabilities affect the behavior and reliability of a system (Takeshi 2013). In the context of reliability and risk analysis, Monte Carlo simulation allows for modeling and evaluating the performance of systems under various operating

and failure conditions. By incorporating probability distributions for key variables, it is possible to estimate metrics such as the probability of system failure, identify critical components, and assess the impact of different risk mitigation strategies(Z. Liu, Feng, and X. e. a. Wang 2020).

This method is especially valuable when analyzing systems with complex structures, where interactions between components and failure dependencies are not apparent. Furthermore, Monte Carlo simulation facilitates the evaluation of what-if scenarios and the performance of sensitivity analyses, contributing to more informed decision making in systems engineering and risk management(ibid.) In summary, Monte Carlo simulation is a powerful technique that, by leveraging random sampling and probabilistic modeling, offers a detailed understanding of reliability and risk in complex systems, overcoming the limitations of traditional analytical methods.

The basic Monte Carlo procedure is as follows:

- Specify the pseudopopulation in symbolic terms such that it can be used to generate samples. This typically means developing a computer algorithm to generate data in a specific way.
- Take a sample from the pseudopopulation (a pseudosample) in ways that reflect the statistical situation of interest, for example, with the same sampling strategy, sample size, etc.

2.3.1 Monte Carlo simulation

Monte Carlo simulation is a versatile mathematical method designed to study stochastic processes and solve complex problems by random sampling. Originating in the 1940s during the development of nuclear weapons at Los Alamos, the method was initially conceived as "games of chance (Casino Monte Carlo in Monaco)" used to explore various phenomena. With the advent of modern computing, the effectiveness of Monte Carlo methods has improved significantly, allowing their application in solving complex scientific and engineering problems. Although historically criticized for being limited to rough estimates, Monte Carlo simulations have become indispensable in fields such as statistical physics, system reliability, and risk analysis due to their ability to model complex and uncertain systems with high accuracy (Kalos and Whitlock 2009).

At the core of Monte Carlo simulations is their stochastic nature, which allows for the modeling of systems governed by random processes rather than deterministic equations such as Newtonian mechanics. For example, in diffusion-limited aggregation (DLA), particles perform random walks until they attach to a growing mass, allowing for the study of fractal properties in the resulting

structures. By relying on random sampling, the method generates results based on sequences of random numbers, where different sequences yield slightly varied results due to statistical error. However, with a sufficiently large number of iterations, these results converge, providing robust and reliable insights into complex systems. This probabilistic framework is particularly effective for modeling natural stochastic processes, such as the interactions of radiation with matter, which are inherently unpredictable but can be accurately described by Monte Carlo methods (D. Landau and Kurt Binder 2021).

A prominent application of Monte Carlo simulation is statistical mechanics, where it is used to estimate thermal averages and sample phase space in many-particle systems. These simulations are essential to understanding equilibrium states in systems where statistical fluctuations play an important role. Monte Carlo methods can effectively capture these fluctuations and their effects, offering a deeper understanding of the behavior of complex physical systems. Furthermore, the technique is widely applied to simulate radiation emission and interaction processes, bridging the gap between theoretical equations and real-world stochastic phenomena (D. Landau and Kurt Binder 2021; Kalos and Whitlock 2009). Monte Carlo simulation also excels in solving practical challenges in various fields. In percolation theory, the method is used to determine critical thresholds, such as the percolation threshold, where an infinite cluster forms in a network. Similarly, DLA simulations allow the study of aggregate growth and structural properties by modeling particles performing random walks. In engineering and risk analysis, Monte Carlo methods are crucial for assessing system reliability, estimating failure probabilities, identifying critical components, and evaluating the effectiveness of risk mitigation strategies. These capabilities make the method invaluable for understanding the behavior and risks of complex systems (D. P. Landau and K. Binder 2014).

In the context of electromagnetic radiation and particle interactions with matter, it's especially valuable because these processes involve inherently probabilistic behavior, such as scattering, absorption, and emission. Then, the interactions between radiation or particles like photons, electrons, or neutrons and matter are governed by quantum and statistical mechanics. These interactions involve stochastic (random) processes, such as:

- Photon absorption or scattering.
- Particle deflection or energy loss.
- Secondary particle production.

- Highly complex geometries and materials, where analytical solutions become impossible.

Monte Carlo simulations handle this complexity by statistically modeling individual particle histories and aggregating the results to predict macroscopic behavior. This method provides a powerful framework to simulate the random, probabilistic nature of radiation and particle interactions with matter, enabling accurate modeling of energy transport in highly complex environments where deterministic methods fail.

The versatility and robustness of Monte Carlo simulations lie in their ability to accurately model uncertainty and variability. By leveraging random sampling and iterative computation, these simulations provide a powerful framework for solving problems that are analytically unsolvable or computationally prohibitive using traditional methods. Their broad applicability, from statistical mechanics and engineering to radiotherapy optimization as is the case here, will be explored in more depth in the next chapter in the part that interests us in mathematical modeling and its programming basis.

2.4 Hybrid Systems in Dosimetric Optimization

Hybrid systems in dosimetric optimization represent an innovative approach that integrates machine learning techniques, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs), with Monte Carlo (MC) simulations to improve the efficiency, accuracy, and scalability of radiotherapy treatment planning, which is what this paper is based on. These systems leverage the strengths of both methodologies: the computational speed and pattern recognition capabilities of deep learning models and the probabilistic accuracy of MC methods, creating a synergistic framework to optimize dose distributions in complex clinical scenarios. The CNN component serves as the initial stage of the hybrid system, rapidly analyzing medical imaging data, such as CT and PET scans, to identify tumor regions and organs at risk (OARs). Furthermore, CNNs are capable of generating preliminary dose predictions that approximate the optimal distribution. For example, predictive denoising approaches such as DeepMCDose have demonstrated their ability to accelerate small beam dose calculations while maintaining high accuracy, significantly reducing computation time compared to traditional MC methods (Neph et al. 2019). Similarly, advanced deep learning models such as Swin UNETR++ use transformer-based architectures to generate dense, high-resolution dose predictions, pushing the boundaries of automation in radiotherapy planning (K. Wang, Tan, and Mcbeth 2023). These CNN-powered approaches lay the foundation for the hybrid system by offering a fast and effective starting

point for its optimization.

Monte Carlo simulations are integrated into the hybrid system as a second stage, refining the initial dose distributions generated by the CNN. This refinement is crucial for modeling the physical interactions of radiation with patient-specific anatomical structures, ensuring that dose calculations are accurate and clinically reliable. Research has shown that combining deep learning with Monte Carlo simulations, as seen in frameworks such as conditional 3D-UNet generative adversarial networks (GANs), enables accurate modeling of heterogeneous phantoms, yielding highly accurate dose predictions even in complex anatomical environments [Mentzel et al., 2022]. Furthermore, hybrid methodologies have shown potential to accelerate radiation transport simulations, as demonstrated by models using CNNs to predict Monte Carlo outcomes with small samples while preserving dosimetric quality (Peng et al. 2019). The use of Python to develop CNN models and C++ libraries, such as Geant4 and ROOT, for Monte Carlo simulations underscores the modular and interoperable design of the hybrid system. Python provides a robust ecosystem for deploying and training machine learning models using libraries such as TensorFlow and PyTorch, while C++ enables accurate and efficient simulation of radiation interactions through established frameworks custom-designed for medical physics applications. By combining these tools, the hybrid system can seamlessly integrate data-driven predictions with physics-based validations, striking a balance between computational efficiency and dosimetric accuracy.

Hybrid systems have demonstrated their ability to address challenges of traditional dosimetric planning, such as variability in treatment quality and high computational costs. By automating key processes and incorporating probabilistic refinement, these systems not only improve the accuracy and consistency of treatment plans, but also offer scalability to diverse clinical settings, such as diabetes management and outcome analysis (Henge et al. 2025). Detection of diabetic retinopathy using a multi-decision inception-ResNet-Blended hybrid model and a deep Siamese convolution neural network for multi-class classification of Alzheimer disease (C. Liu et al. 2023) and many other fields in translational medicine and engineering. This integration of machine learning and Monte Carlo methods represents a significant advancement in radiotherapy, paving the way for highly precise, personalized cancer treatments that are efficient and clinically robust (Neph et al. 2019; Peng et al. 2019; Mentzel et al. 2022; K. Wang, Tan, and Mcbeth 2023).

Chapter 3: Literature Review

3.1 Overview

The field of radiotherapy optimization has seen remarkable advances in the last decades. With the integration of computational techniques such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and Monte Carlo simulations, the accuracy and personalization of cancer treatment have improved significantly. The aim of this chapter is to critically evaluate state-of-the-art methods, identify gaps in the existing literature, and provide a foundation for the hybrid model proposed in this thesis. A comprehensive review of the literature reveals that while individual techniques have shown promise, combining them into a hybrid model can address specific limitations and improve dosimetric outcomes. This chapter delves into CNNs, Monte Carlo simulations and their synergistic potential in radiotherapy dosimetry, however, since in the previous chapter we talked about all the important theory and laid the foundations to understand the project, in this one we will focus on the object of study, such as the variables to take into account, CNN (How to train the NN), Radiotherapy (Biological basis of the study), hybrid system (use of python [train the NN] and C++ [train the MCS]; linking these two using ROOT (by CERN)).

- **Neural Network Convolutional (CNN)**
- **Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS)**
- **Hybrid System**
- **Radiotherapy**

3.2 CNN

CNN Fundamentals Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have emerged as a cornerstone of modern machine learning, particularly in image analysis and pattern recognition tasks. CNNs are designed to automatically and adaptively learn spatial feature hierarchies from input data through a series of convolutional, pooled, and fully connected layers. The architecture of CNNs allows them to capture local and global features, making them particularly suitable for analyzing medical images such as CT and MRI scans (Yann LeCun, Bengio, and G. Hinton 2015). In line with this, a brief introduction from simple neural networks to convolutional networks will be shown, in order to better understand the context. Artificial neural networks, commonly referred to as “neural networks,” have been motivated since their inception by the recognition that the human brain computes in a completely different way than the conventional digital computer. A neural network is a machine that is designed to model the way the brain performs a particular task or function of interest; The network is usually implemented using electronic components or simulated in software on a digital computer. A neural network is a massively parallel distributed processor, composed of simple processing units, that has a natural propensity to store experiential knowledge and make it available for use. It resembles the brain in two ways (Nielsen 2015):

1. The network acquires knowledge of its environment through a learning.
2. Connection strengths between neurons, known as synaptic weights, are used to store the acquired knowledge.

To begin, will explain a type of artificial neuron called perceptron, Then will move on to sigmoid neuron and from there we will jump to the convolutional neural network(CNN).

3.2.1 Perceptrons

were developed in the 1950s and 1960s by scientist Frank Rosenblatt, inspired by earlier work by Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts. Today, it is more common to use other models of artificial neurons: the main model of neuron used is one called a sigmoid neuron (which by forming more layers and complex connections make up other types of neural networks on which there is the CNN, on which we will focus). We'll get to sigmoid neurons shortly. But to understand why sigmoid neurons are defined the way they are, it's worth taking the time to first understand perceptrons.

Figure 3.2.1: Perceptron

So how do perceptrons work? A perceptron takes multiple binary inputs. According to (Figure 3.2.1), a perceptron takes multiple binary, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m , as we can see, producing a single binary output. In general, you could have more or fewer inputs. Rosenblatt proposed a simple rule for calculating the output. He introduced weights w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m and real numbers that express the importance of the respective inputs to the output. The output of the neuron, 0 or 1, is determined by whether the weighted sum $\sum_j w_j \cdot x_j$ is less than or greater than a threshold value. Like weights, the threshold is a real number that is a parameter of the neuron. To put it in more precise algebraic terms (Teuwen and Moriakov 2020):

$$\text{output } (v) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \sum_j w_j x_j \leq \text{threshold} \\ 1 & \text{if } \sum_j w_j x_j > \text{threshold} \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

That's all there is to how a perceptron works! That's the basic mathematical model. One way you can think about the perceptron is that it is a device that makes decisions by weighing evidence. Let me give an example. It is not a very realistic example, but it is easy to understand:

We then see that input 00, produces output 1, since $(2)0+(2)0+3 = 3$, is positive. Here, I have introduced the symbol, to make the multiplications explicit. Similar calculations show that the inputs 01 and 10 produce the output 1. But input 11 produces output 0, since $(2)1+(2)1+3 = 1$ is negative.

Let's simplify the way we describe perceptrons. The condition, $\sum_j w_j \cdot x_j > threshold$, is cumbersome, and we can make two notational changes to simplify it. The first change is to write $\sum_j w_j \cdot x_j$, as a dot product, $w \cdot x = \sum_j w_j \cdot x_j$, where w and x are vectors whose components are the weights and inputs, respectively. The second change is to move the *threshold* to the other side of the inequality and replace it with what is known as the bias of the perceptron, $b \equiv threshold$. Using the bias instead of the *threshold*, the perceptron rule can be rewritten:

$$\text{output} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } w \cdot x + b \leq 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } w \cdot x + b > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

You can think of bias as a measure of how easy it is to get the perceptron to output a 1. Or, to put it in more biological terms, bias is a measure of how easy it is to get the perceptron to activate. For a perceptron with a really large bias, it is extremely easy for it to output a 1. But if the bias is very negative, then it is difficult for the perceptron to output a 1 (Haykin 1996).

3.2.2 Sigmoid neurons

The Sigmoid function, one of the most widely used activation functions in neural networks, transforms a continuous input into a range between 0 and 1, making it easy to interpret as a probability (Goodfellow et al. 2020). Mathematically, it is defined as $\sigma(z) \equiv 1/(1 + e^{-z})$, where z is the input. Its main advantage lies in smoothing outputs, allowing models to handle nonlinear data efficiently.

In deep neural networks, the Sigmoid function is applied on individual nodes to introduce non-linearity, which is crucial for modeling complex relationships. However, it has limitations such as “gradient vanishing,” which can make training deep networks difficult (Nwankpa et al. 2018). For this reason, other functions such as ReLU have gained popularity in certain contexts. The Sigmoid function remains relevant in specific applications, such as the last layers of neural networks dedicated to binary classification tasks. Its probabilistic interpretation and the smoothness of its output make it a standard choice in scenarios where these properties are essential.

Okay, let me describe the sigmoid neuron. We'll depict sigmoid neurons in the same way we depicted perceptrons:

Figure 3.2.2: Sigmoid

Just like a perceptron (Figure 3.2.2), the sigmoid neuron has inputs, x_1, x_2, \dots . But instead of being just 0 or 1, these inputs can also take on any values between 0 and 1. So, for instance, 0.738... is a valid input for a sigmoid neuron.

So, the sigmoid function is called σ , and is defined by:

$$\sigma(z) \equiv \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}. \quad (3.3)$$

To put it all a little more explicitly, the output of a sigmoid neuron with inputs x_1, x_2, \dots , weights w_1, w_2, \dots , and bias b is:

$$\frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(-\sum_j w_j x_j - b\right)} \quad (3.4)$$

At first sight, sigmoid neurons appear very different to perceptrons. The algebraic form of the sigmoid function may seem opaque and forbidding if you're not already familiar with it. In fact, there are many similarities between perceptrons and sigmoid neurons, and the algebraic form of the sigmoid function turns out to be more of a technical detail than a true barrier to understanding (Nielsen 2015).

3.2.3 Covolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are an architecture specialized in processing gridstructured data such as images. Unlike densely connected networks, CNNs employ convolutional layers that learn local filters, allowing them to extract hierarchical spatial features from the inputs. These layers operate by applying a set of kernels over small regions of the input, thereby significantly reducing the number of parameters and improving computational efficiency (Y. LeCun et al. 1998). CNNs are typically composed of convolution, pooling, and dense layers, which facilitate the detection of local and global patterns. Furthermore, the use of modern techniques such as dropout and batch normalization has improved their performance and generalization capabilities (Ioffe 2015). Thanks to these properties, CNNs are widely used in computer vision, including tasks such as image classification, semantic segmentation, and object detection. Despite their limitations, such as the need for large datasets and computational resources, they have proven to be a powerful tool in multiple fields, including medicine, robotics, and astronomy (Krizhevsky, Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton 2012) (Krizhevsky et al., 2012). Their design inspires more advanced architectures such as deep vision networks and recurrent convolutional networks.

CNNs are very different from other pattern recognition algorithms in that they combine both feature extraction and classification. 3.2.3 shows an example of a simple schematic representation of a basic CNN. This simple network consists of five different layers: an input layer, a convolution layer, a pooling layer, a fully connected layer, and an output layer. These layers are divided into two parts: feature extraction and classification. Feature extraction consists of an input layer, a convolution layer, and a pooling layer, while classification consists of a fully connected layer and an output layer. The input layer specifies a fixed size for the input images, which is resized if necessary. The image is then convolved with multiple kernels learned using weights shared by the convolution layer. The pooling layer then reduces the size of the image while trying to maintain the information contained within. The results of feature extraction are known as feature maps. Classification combines the extracted features in the fully connected layers. Finally, there is one output neuron for each object category in the output layer. The output of the classification part is the classification result.

Figure 3.2.3: CNN

Lets to describe the mathematically, the convolution $(xw)(a)$ of functions x and w is defined in all dimensions as:

$$(x * w)(a) = \int x(t)w(a - t) dt, \quad (3.5)$$

where a is in R^n for any $n \geq 1$, and the integral is replaced by its higher-dimensional variant. To understand the idea behind convolutions, it is interesting to pick the Gaussian function $w(a) = \exp(-x^2)$, as an example. If we were taking a photo with a camera and shaking the camera a bit, the blurry picture would be the real picture x convolved with a Gaussian function w .

In the terminology of convolutional neural networks, x is called the input, w is called the filter or kernel, and the output is often referred to as activation, or feature map. Note that we modeled the input and kernel in (5) as a continuous function. Due to the discrete nature of image sensors, this will not be the case in practice and it is more realistic to assume that parameter t is discrete. If we assume that this is the case, then we can define the discrete convolution

$$(x * w)(a) = \sum_a x(t)w(t - a), \quad (3.6)$$

where a runs over all values in the space, and can be in any dimension. In deep learning, usually x is a multidimensional array of data and the kernel w involves learnable parameters and usually has finite support, that is, there are only finitely many values a for which $w(a)$ is nonzero. This means that we can implement (6) as a finite sum-mation. The definition of (6) is independent of dimension, but in medical imaging we will mainly be working with 2- or 3-dimensional convolutions:

$$(I * K)(i, j) = \sum_m \sum_n I(m, n)K(i - m, j - n), \quad (3.7)$$

Or,

$$(I * K)(i, j, k) = \sum_m \sum_n \sum_\ell I(m, n, \ell)K(i - m, j - n, k - \ell). \quad (3.8)$$

The convolutions, (5) and (6) are commutative, which means that $IK = KI$, so that we can also write (7) as:

$$(I * K)(i, j) = \sum_m \sum_n I(i - m, j - n)K(m, n). \quad (3.9)$$

As K has finite support, this a priori infinite sum becomes finite. Some neural network libraries also implement an operation called the cross-correlation, but from a deep learning perspective these operations are equivalent, as one weight set can be directly translated into the other. Lets to describe in tensor way to simplify the eq(8),

Hence, we rewrite the terms:

input: $I(m, n, l) \rightarrow X_{(i+p)(j+q)}^m$, filter weights: $K(i - m, j - n, k - l) \rightarrow W_{pq}^{k,m}$. The bias b^k , is added at the end.

So we obtain the (10)equ:

$$Y_{ijk} = \sum_m \sum_{pq} X_{(i+p)(j+q)}^m W_{pq}^{k,m} + b^k \quad (3.10)$$

This equation describes the same convolutional process as your original equation, but with CNN-specific notation and terms. The conceptual relationship: I : The generic input now becomes X , which represents the activation values or pixels of the previous layers in a CNN. K : The convolutional filters are now W , where each filter learns specific values during training. Bias (b_k): This is included as part of learning in neural networks (Haykin 1996).

3.3 Monte Carlo applied to dosimetry

The Monte Carlo method is a probabilistic technique that uses simulations based on random numbers to solve mathematical and physical problems. It was developed during the 1940s at Los Alamos, in the context of nuclear research, and has proven to be an essential tool in fields such as statistics, physics, biology, and engineering (Metropolis and Ulam, 1949). This method is based on the repetition of computational experiments, generating distributions of results through random sampling. Its main advantage lies in its ability to address complex systems that cannot be treated analytically. Basing this on a computational basis, we obtain the Monte Carlo simulation that extends this method to the modeling of physical phenomena, especially those governed by stochastic processes. In the field of radiation, it is used to model interactions between particles and matter, allowing the calculation of trajectories, deposited energy, and spatial distributions of radiation. These simulations are fundamental in medical applications such as the planning of radiotherapy treatments (D. P. Landau and K. Binder 2014).

The basic idea behind a Monte Carlo simulation is to represent the solution of complex equations by averaging the results obtained through multiple random realizations. This can be expressed mathematically as:

$$I \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N f(x_i) \quad (3.11)$$

where,

- I : Expected value of the integral or solution.
- N : Total number of iterations.
- $f(x_i)$: Function evaluated in each random sample x_i .

Lets see one of the best known examples when making an introduction to the Monte Carlo method and its simulation, where we can better visualize what was previously stated together with equation (11).

Figure 3.3.1: Pi estimation[Overflow Python]

Here we can see in the 3.3.1 how the total flow is counted, which is the total number of points (blue plus pink "N"), and the number of pi is estimated according to the number of points found within the circumference (Blue points "I"). So the more shots or the greater the flow, the greater the precision of the number pi ($\approx \pi$).

When talking the radiation emission and its interaction with matter are inherently stochastic processes. In radiotherapy, Monte Carlo methods are used to model these interactions, providing accurate dose calculations. Programs such as EGSnrc, Geant4, and MCNP implement Monte Carlo simulations to predict dose distribution in heterogeneous tissues, overcoming the limitations of traditional analytical methods (Kalos and Whitlock 2009).

In the context of radiation, the particle transport equation describes the flow of particles (e.g., photons or electrons and another particules types) through a medium. The Monte Carlo method solves this equation by simulating the trajectory of millions of individual particles and recording their interactions. Mathematically, the process is represented as:

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E) = \int_0^s \mu(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E) \phi(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E) ds \quad (3.12)$$

Where,

- $\psi(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E)$: Spatial and energetic distribution of particles.
- $\mu(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E)$: Attenuation coefficient.

- $\phi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega, E)$: Particle flow.

In radiotherapy, the goal is to optimize dose delivery to tumor tissue while minimizing the impact on healthy tissues. Monte Carlo methods are essential for:

- Calculating dose distributions in heterogeneous tissues with high accuracy.
- Modeling radiotherapy devices such as linear accelerators.
- Validating clinical planning algorithms.

For example, in modern applications, Monte Carlo simulations are combined with neural networks to accelerate calculations while maintaining high levels of accuracy (Neph et al. 2019; Peng et al. 2019).

Figure 3.3.2: Geant4 [Doses Distribution]

Monte Carlo simulation is the gold standard for dose calculations in radiotherapy, as shown in figure 3.3.2 modeled at GEANT4 (Root-CERN)(Allison, K. Amako, JEA Apostolakis, et al. 2006; Agostinelli et al. 2003), due to its unmatched accuracy in modeling radiation-tissue interaction. Although its main challenge is computational cost, improvements in hardware and hybrid algorithms, such as integration with neural networks, have made it an increasingly viable tool for clinical planning, as we will see in Chapter 5.

3.4 Hybrid Model

Hybrid systems have emerged as a potential solution to address the challenges inherent in radiotherapy dosimetric optimization. They combine the strengths of high-precision methods, such as Monte Carlo simulations, with the speed and predictive capacity of convolutional neural networks (CNN). This system seeks to overcome the individual limitations of each method: the high computational demand of Monte Carlo and the potential loss of accuracy in CNN approximations (Jiang, Q. Ma, and Zhu 2020). The central concept of a hybrid system is to divide the computational process into two complementary stages. First, CNNs generate fast initial predictions of dose distributions, based on historical data and learned patterns. These predictions are then fine-tuned by Monte Carlo simulations, which introduce detailed physical refinement based on stochastic interactions. This integration not only significantly reduces computational time, but also maintains high standards of clinical accuracy (Neph et al. 2019; Jiang, Q. Ma, and Zhu 2020).

Although there is no mathematical basis to explain this, we will make our own which is linear and may be useful to understand how this hybrid system proposed here works,

$$D_{CNN}(i, j, k) = f_{CNN}(I(i, j, k), W) \quad (3.13)$$

Where:

- $D_{CNN}(i, j, k)$ is the predicted initial dose distribution.
- f_{CNN} represents the function mapped by the convolutional neural network.
- $I_{(i,j,k)}$ are the medical images (CT, PET).
- W are the learned weights of the model.

Hence,

$$D_{final}(i, j, k) = D_{pred}(i, j, k) + \Delta D_{MC}(i, j, k), \quad (3.14)$$

were:

- $D_{Treatment}(i, j, k)$ is the refined distribution after applying Monte Carlo.

- $DMC(i, j, k)$ represents the correction calculated by Monte Carlo simulations to account for complex physical effects.

Figure 3.4.1: PET/CT

Now I will give a vivid and partially novel example, view figure 3.4.1, that is deeply related to this topic, computed tomography (CT-a,b), has been with us for about 55 years, clearly helping us to make a better diagnosis of different types of studies, but we will focus on cancer. However, this study takes into account the anatomical part and since the internal system of our body is dynamic, we needed something that would help us with this. From there, something even newer than (CT-a,b) emerged, which we call Positron Emission Tomography (PET-d), which was useful until just 35 years ago. This study takes into account the physiological part of the human body. And so, around the 2000s, these studies were combined to create one of the first hybrid imaging and diagnostic studies, the PET/CT Scan (c), which is based on the superposition of masks from these studies (b/d) to improve visualization (Zhang-Yin, Girard, and Bertaux 2022).

Recent studies have demonstrated the potential of hybrid systems in clinical settings. For example, (Neph et al. 2019), combined a 3D neural network with Monte Carlo simulations to predict doses in image-guided radiotherapy treatments. The results showed that this hybrid approach not only improved the accuracy of the calculations but also reduced computational times by more than 50%. Similarly, Zhu et al. (2019) implemented a hybrid model for optimization in intensity-modulated radiotherapy (IMRT), achieving clinically acceptable dose distributions in significantly shorter times. Hybrid systems represent a significant evolution in radiotherapy planning, combining the best of

both worlds: the efficiency of CNNs and the accuracy of Monte Carlo. Their implementation in clinical contexts not only promises faster and more personalized treatments, but also lays the foundation for future innovations in radiation dosimetry.

3.5 Radiotherapy

Radiotherapy is the most common modality for treating human cancers. Eighty percent of cancer patients require radiotherapy at some point or another, either for curative or palliative purposes. For optimal results, a judicious balance is required between the total radiotherapy dose delivered and the threshold limit of the surrounding normal critical tissues. To obtain better tumor control with a higher dose, normal tissues must be protected from radiation injury.

Radiotherapy treatment can only be effective if used in an appropriate clinical context. Attempting radical treatment in a patient with metastatic disease or who is likely to die soon from heart or lung disease is inappropriate. These decisions require a delicate balance of judgement between therapeutic optimism and skepticism and must be firmly based on a good clinical history and examination. The physician must be able to synthesise all the information about the patient, the tumour, investigations and previous treatment to make a decision about whether to give radiotherapy and, if so, with radical or palliative intent. Comorbidities such as diabetes or vascular disease, which might affect the toxicity of treatment, must also be considered. Sometimes the decision to offer radiotherapy may be relatively straightforward if the disease is common, treatment is effective and standardised, histological features are well categorised and images are easy to interpret. Some breast cancers fit well into this category.

3.5.1 Diagnostic imaging

Advances in techniques have made it possible to treat complex targets at high doses with pinpoint accuracy and dramatically reduce dose to preserve healthy tissue. Other advances include the use of linear accelerators with integrated MRI or PET scanners, allowing for greater tissue definition during treatment than without them and allowing for adaptive therapy as tumor size or location changes during treatment.

Figure 3.5.1: [PET/IMR Mask]

Where, (A) Two-dimensional planning image quality is poor and treatment fields (the area inside the black line) are large; as planning and imaging techniques improved, treatment by intensity-modulated radiotherapy (B) and stereotactic body radiotherapy (C) techniques were enabled. The dark blue lines in (B) and (C) represent the planning target volume; the other coloured lines represent the different isodose lines, so in other words, this is what we are trying to do here, attack the core or target of the tumor, together with areas that we will soon see with less radiation and try not to disperse the radiation to the organs at risk (healthy tissue). As we can see in the (Figure. 3.5.1) (Chandra et al. 2021) and to which we refer to the *Gtv* that we can see in the image 3.5.3.

3.5.2 Dosimetric Planning

CT scans are transferred digitally to the target volume localisation console using an electronic network system which must be compliant with DICOM 3 and DICOM RT protocols (Fig. 3.5.2). The GTV, CTV, PTV, body contour and normal organs are outlined by a team of radiation oncologist, specialist radiologist and planning technician, with appropriate training. Where MRI is the optimal imaging modality for tumours such as the prostate, uterus, brain, head and neck and sarcomas, it is incorporated into target volume definition by image fusion. Treatment planning based on MR images alone is reported, but more commonly CT and MR images are co-registered, ideally scanning using a flat MRI couch top to aid matching. PET or PET-CT images may give additional information for head and neck tumours, lymphomas, lung and gynaecological tumours, and SPECT for brain tumours. Multimodality image fusion of all these images in the treatment planning process is ideal for accurate delineation of the target.

Figure 3.5.2: [Radiotherapy Planning]

Once the treatment plan has been generated, it must be validated both clinically and physically. Radiation oncologists review the plan to ensure it meets the stated objectives, while physical simulations verify that the radiation team correctly executes the plan using phantoms. Quality protocols also ensure that the process meets international standards set by organizations such as AAPM and ICRU (Radiological Units (ICRU) 1987). The use of advanced technologies, such as treatment planning systems (TPS) integrated with artificial intelligence and machine learning tools, is transforming dosimetric planning. Neural network-based algorithms are beginning to predict dose distributions, reducing the time needed to develop personalized plans. In this context, dosimetric planning not only ensures treatment effectiveness and safety, but is also positioned as a key area for future innovations in radiotherapy (Kearney et al. 2018).

Figure 3.5.3: [ICRU target volume definitions showing GTV, CTV, PTV, treated and irradiated volume.][Reproduced with permission from ICRU (1993) Prescribing, Recording and Reporting Photon Beam Therapy. ICRU report 50]

Dosimetric planning is a fundamental process in radiotherapy for a better understanding of what will be explained here, see the image 3.5.3, designed to maximize the effectiveness of the treatment on the tumor while minimizing adverse effects on healthy tissues. This process begins with the definition of volumes of interest according to the standards established by the ICRU (International Commission on Radiation Units and Measurements). Among these, the macroscopic volume of the tumor, known as GTV (Gross Tumor Volume), represents the region visible in medical images, such as CT, MRI or PET. From this volume, the CTV (Clinical Target Volume) is defined, which includes an additional margin for possible microscopic tumor cells, and the PTV (Planning Target Volume), which considers additional margins to compensate for patient movements and positioning errors. In addition, the organs at risk (OAR, Organs at Risk) are identified, which are critical structures close to the tumor, such as the spinal cord, heart or lungs, whose exposure to radiation must be minimized to avoid severe complications (Radiological Units (ICRU) 1976). A key aspect of dosimetric planning is the analysis of dose-volume histograms (DVHs), which allow the assessment of dose distribution in target volumes and organs at risk. These curves show the relationship between delivered dose and tissue volume, ensuring that the PTV receives at least 95% of the prescribed dose while minimizing

dose to the OARs. A flat curve on a DVH indicates a homogeneous dose distribution, a critical goal in treatment planning (Ezzell et al. 2009).

There are several methods for performing dosimetric planning. In more advanced approaches, such as 3D conformal radiation therapy (3D-CRT), intensity-modulated radiation therapy (IMRT), and volumetric modulated arc therapy (VMAT), three-dimensional imaging is used to create plans that conform the dose to the shape of the tumor while respecting the limits established for the OARs. IMRT, for example, allows modulating the intensity of radiation fields to obtain more precise dose distributions tailored to the patient's anatomy (Yu 1995). VMAT, on the other hand, improves the speed and efficiency of treatment by delivering the dose during the rotation of the linear accelerator around the patient (Otto 2008). Optimization plays a crucial role in modern planning. In particular, inverse optimization is a method where clinical objectives are first defined, such as the desired dose at the PTV and the constraints for the OARs, and then the dose distribution that best meets these objectives is calculated. In addition, Monte Carlo simulations have established themselves as the gold standard for dosimetric calculations due to their high accuracy in modeling stochastic particle-tissue interactions, especially in complex regions such as bone-tissue interfaces (C.-M. Ma et al. 2001).

3.5.3 Radiobiology

Ionizing radiation causes damage to living tissues through a series of molecular events, such as photoelectric, Compton, and Auger effects, which depends on the radiation energy and particle type. Since human tissues contain 80% water, the major radiation damage is due to aqueous free radicals, generated by the action of radiation on water. The main free radicals resulting from aqueous radiolysis are OH , H , e_{aq}^- , HO_2 , H_3O^+ , etc.). These free radicals react with cellular macromolecules, such as DNA, RNA, proteins, membranes, etc., and cause cellular dysfunction and mortality. These reactions occur in both tumor cells and normal cells when exposed to threshold radiation.

As we can see in the image 3.5.4 the Radiation and cell kill Ionising radiation causes wide-ranging molecular damage throughout cells by the production of ionised atoms, which cause breakage of chemical bonds, production of free radicals and damage to DNA. Most clinically significant effects of radiotherapy are due to irreparable DNA lesions which result in sterilisation – a loss of proliferative cells' ability for sustained cell division. In tumours, loss of proliferative ability by all the cells of the

Figure 3.5.4: [Radiobiology Schema Interaction]

tumour is a necessary condition for tumour cure. Partial sterilisation of the tumour cell population results in tumour stasis or regression, giving a clinical remission, followed by regrowth of the tumour from those cells which have retained their proliferative ability. In self-renewing normal tissues, sterilisation of proliferative cells leaves the tissues unable to provide replacements for cells that are ordinarily being lost at a constant rate from the tissue, and initiates a rundown of the mature cells of the tissue. Proliferative sterilisation is often referred to as cell kill, with those cells that retain long-term proliferative ability being described as survivors (De Mello, Tavares, and Mountzios 2019).

Chapter 4: Methodology

The methodology proposed for this project is designed to address current limitations in radiotherapy dosimetric planning by developing a hybrid system that combines machine learning techniques and Monte Carlo simulations. This approach seeks to leverage the complementary strengths of convolutional neural networks (CNN) and advanced probabilistic methods offered by the Monte Carlo Method to ensure an optimized radiotherapy plan. The implementation of the hybrid system is based on a structured sequence of stages ranging from the collection and preprocessing of medical data, to the validation of the system in simulated clinical cases. Each phase has been carefully designed to meet the objectives of maximizing tumor irradiation, minimizing damage to healthy tissues.

Through this methodology, it is expected not only to develop an innovative and scalable tool, but also to contribute to the advancement of the state of the art in dosimetric optimization, providing a solution that can be integrated into real clinical environments.

4.1 Overview

The proposed framework is a hybrid system designed to optimize radiotherapy dosimetric planning by combining convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with Monte Carlo simulations. The system begins with the collection and preprocessing of medical imaging data, such as CT, MRI and PET scans, and clinical annotations defining tumor regions and organs at risk (OARs). Preprocessing steps include normalization, segmentation, and feature extraction to ensure that the data is prepared for further analysis. CNNs are then used to analyze the preprocessed data, identifying tumor regions and OARs while simultaneously predicting an initial volumetric dose distribution based on patterns learned from historical treatment plans.

Monte Carlo simulations are then used to refine the dose predictions generated by the CNN. These simulations model radiation interactions with anatomical structures to produce highly accurate, patient-specific dose distributions. By integrating CNN and Monte Carlo components, the framework achieves computational efficiency and dosimetric accuracy, enabling the generation of optimized

radiotherapy treatment plans. The final output of the system is evaluated using metrics such as Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Conformity Index (CI), and Homogeneity Index (HI) to ensure the quality of segmentation and dose distribution.

The results are further validated against clinical reference plans and traditional methods such as knowledge-based planning. This hybrid framework reduces computational overhead while maintaining high levels of accuracy and adaptability, providing a practical and scalable solution to improve treatment outcomes in radiotherapy.

4.2 Model

The process is divided into several phases, ensuring a structured and efficient development process, as described below:

Medical Data Collection and Preprocessing

This first step is the search for data sources, so we will search public repositories, such as TCIA and OpenKBP, which provide CT and PET scans along with clinical annotations, thus ensuring the use of reliable data. Images are preprocessed by converting them to DICOM format, normalizing intensity values, and segmenting anatomical structures such as tumors and organs at risk (OAR).

CNN Module

The second phase will focus on the CNN module, which is designed to analyze medical images and predict initial dose distributions. Using architectures such as U-Net, the CNN is trained with historical treatment plans to identify tumor regions and OARs while estimating volumetric dose distributions. The output of this module includes segmented masks and an initial dose prediction map, which provides a basis for further refinement.

Monte Carlo Simulation

The third phase uses the Monte Carlo simulation module using GEANT4 (CERN) and creating the source code, which will serve to define the initial dose distributions generated by the CNN. This module employs probabilistic models to simulate the interaction of radiation with anatomical tissues,

achieving high accuracy in dose calculations. The CNN predictions will serve as input parameters for the simulations, which then produce an optimized dose distribution for the patient.

Formation of the Hybrid System.

The results of both modules are integrated in the optimization process, where the system fuses the CNN predictions and Monte Carlo refinements to create a comprehensive radiotherapy treatment plan. This plan is then structured using clinical software such as Eclipse or RayStation, which will give the feasibility of the hybrid system with existing workstations.

The Evaluation Phase

involves validating the system's performance using metrics such as Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) for segmentation accuracy and Conformity Index (CI) and Homogeneity Index (HI) for dose quality assessment. The hybrid system's results are compared to traditional methods and clinical reference plans to demonstrate its effectiveness.

Tuning and Optimization Phase

This includes refining the CNN architecture, fine-tuning simulation parameters, and re-evaluating the results in various clinical scenarios, ensuring that the system meets the demands of modern clinical environments while advancing radiotherapy planning.

4.2.1 Dataset

The success of the proposed hybrid system for dosimetric optimization in radiotherapy relies heavily on a clinically relevant dataset. This dataset will serve as a basis for training, validation, and evaluation of the system, ensuring its practical applicability. The dataset will be obtained from trusted public repositories, such as The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA), which provides anonymized medical images in DICOM format, including CT, PET, and MRI scans; OpenKBP, a dataset specifically designed for dosimetric optimization that includes dose distributions and treatment plans; and the Medical Segmentation Decathlon (MSD), which has segmented images for training and validation in anatomical segmentation tasks.

The dataset will include key components such as medical images (CT and PET scans) with

resolutions typically of 512 x 512 pixels and slice intervals of 1 to 5 mm (these are the standard measurements in conventional radiotherapy plans). Clinical annotations will accompany the image data, specifying regions of interest, such as tumors and organs at risk (OARs), as well as clinically approved treatment plans (the plans given by generalists in radiotherapy) and dose distributions. In addition, the dataset will provide segmentation masks for tumors and OARs, essential for supervised training of the CNN model.

TCIA

A public repository that offers anonymized medical images in DICOM format, including modalities such as CT, PET and MRI. It is an important source of data since it offers us the variability and certainty of being reliable data. Below we leave the link.

The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA): <https://www.cancerimagingarchive.net/>

OpenKBP

OpenKBP (Open Knowledge-Based Planning). Designed specifically for dosimetric optimization, this dataset includes medical images, dose distributions, and treatment plans. We will use it for the development and validation of automated planning systems. Below we leave the link.

OpenKBP Dataset: <http://medicaldecathlon.com/>

Medical Segmentation Decathlon (MSD)

This repository provides segmented images of different modalities and cancer types, useful for training anatomical segmentation models, below we leave the link.

MSD: <http://medicaldecathlon.com/> We will use the "Medical Segmentation Decathlon "(MSD)" repository, more specifically "Task01BrainTumour", which contains magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) images of brain tumors with annotated segmentations, lets to talk about the important points: Channels, Labels and the Data Format:

Input Modalities (Image Channels)

Each volume in the dataset has 4 input channels corresponding to different MRI sequences:

- FLAIR (Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery): Highlights edema (swelling around the tumor).
- T1-weighted (T1w): Good differentiation of anatomical structures.
- T1-weighted with contrast (T1Gd): Highlights regions with contrast uptake (active tumor).
- T2-weighted (T2w): Useful for observing tumor structure and inflammation.

(Each image has a size of $240 \times 240 \times 155$ (X, Y, Z) pixels)

Segmentation Labels

Each voxel in the segmentation has a label value that indicates the structure of the tumor:

Label	Description	Interpretation
0	Background	No tumor
1	Non-enhancing tumor (necrosis)	Necrotic area of the tumor
2	Peritumoral edema	Surrounding inflammation
3	Enhancing tumor	Active area of the tumor

Table 4.2.1: Labels

Data Format

The data is in NIFTI (*.nii.gz*) format, which is a standard in medical imaging, the structure of the dataset follows the BraTS (Brain Tumor Segmentation) convention. Normally, MRI values should be normalized (mean 0, variance 1) before training, which will be done.

4.2.2 Data Pre-Processing

Before using the dataset, preprocessing steps will be applied, including intensity normalization to ensure uniformity across images, segmentation to isolate relevant regions, and splitting the dataset into training (70), validation (20) and test (10) subsets. These steps will prepare the data for effective use in training and evaluating the model. The CNN component of the hybrid system will use the dataset to learn to identify tumor regions and OARs and to predict initial dose distributions. Then, use this data in Monte Carlo simulation that will further refine these predictions by leveraging the anatomical and dose information provided by the dataset to generate accurate, patient-specific dose distributions. This will play a vital role in training the CNN with real, clinically relevant data and ensuring that the Monte Carlo simulations accurately reflect clinical scenarios. This dataset forms the backbone of the project, driving its success in improving radiotherapy dosimetric planning.

Figure 4.2.1: Pre-Processed image [Left] and label [Right] of the Brain Tumor. (Original images obtained from Kaggle)

The images are collected and processed to allow for better training of the convolutional neural network (CNN). To do this, the program developed in Python goes through the location of all the images and extracts them one by one, then takes a specific number of slices that allow easy visualization of the tumor4.2.1. To improve the training process, the images and labeled images are converted to grayscale and their size is reduced to 224x224 pixels. After processing, the images are saved in a new folder, separated by channels (Each channel represents a different examination performed on the brain of the same patient but all is the same kind in this case MRI, just change that the channels correspond to different magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) modalities used to capture different characteristics of the brain tumor.). Below is an example of the preprocessed images and the resulting processed images and labels 4.2.2.

Figure 4.2.2: Processed image [Left] and label [Right]

Furthermore, since each brain image has four different versions, representing four tests performed on the same brain (the same medical case), the processed images are separated by channels, so that during modeling, training tests can be performed by separate channels, or a single training for the four channels at the same time, this already depends on which is the most favorable method that will be seen with the performance of the neural network. Below is the same brain slice (same medical case), but in four different channels 4.2.3:

Figure 4.2.3: Processed image separated by channels

This allows you to experiment not only with the hyperparameters when modeling, but also with the way the inputs are structured, either by channel, or with an image that collects the characteristics of the four channels in one, for example with a convolution or superposition. It is important to mention that the labels of the images that will be used in training are also stored in a different folder, separated by channels.

4.2.3 CNN Module

To train the model, the generated labels are segmented into three distinct regions, each represented by a different colour to indicate the different levels of the tumour. As input, the model receives four grayscale images with a resolution of 224x224 pixels. The output of the model is a segmented image in which two areas within the tumour are identified, represented in different levels of grey (light grey and dark grey), while the areas without the presence of a tumour are shown in black. This segmentation allows the different affected regions to be accurately distinguished and facilitates the analysis of the tumour 4.2.4.

Figure 4.2.4: CNN Model

To improve training and prediction, before using the images with the model, another processing is performed that improves the visibility of the tumor, changing the Gamma by a percentage value above the average color value of the image, as shown 4.2.5. This variation in the gamma value causes the area of the image that is above the average color to be illuminated, and the rest to be darkened, thus highlighting the tumor sections, improving the system's ability to identify these regions.

Figure 4.2.5: Original image [left] and image with increased gamma [right]

The contours of the most illuminated section are identified, and in case the identified area is assessed as a possible tumor, the mask of the most illuminated section is superimposed on the original image, thus helping the model to more easily identify the tumor section 4.2.6.

Figure 4.2.6: Contour Identification

To develop the image segmentation model, which identifies and delimits a specific area in response to a series of inputs, it is proposed to use as a starting point an Encoder-Decoder architecture, commonly used in image segmentation tasks. In addition, to preserve low-level information and avoid the loss of important details, skip connections can be incorporated. These connections allow maintaining the boundary information and improving segmentation accuracy 4.2.7.

Figure 4.2.7: Proposed model UNet

To preserve low-level information and maintain contour delineation accuracy, skip connections are incorporated. In this model, multiple convolutional layers are employed to extract relevant features from each block, followed by a pooling function that reduces their size and allows for a more compact representation of the information. In the case of the model used, the convolutional layers use several different filters which are the ones that find relevant patterns for tumor identification. Each block has three convolutional layers, and each convolutional layer has several processing filters. The smaller the search resolution, the more filters each convolutional layer will have. In addition, the number of

times the image resolution is reduced in each block is the same as the number of times it is increased, and in the same proportion, with the aim of reaching the initial resolution again at the end of the convolutional layers of the network, resulting in an image with the same resolution as the input image, but with the tumor section highlighted. As a result, the final implemented model follows this structure 4.2.8.

Figure 4.2.8: Final model UNet

To evaluate the effectiveness of different models and determine the optimal configuration, various combinations of the network’s hyper parameters are experimented with. This process allows each model to be assigned a rating, facilitating the selection of the most accurate and efficient one. Then, in each executed process or iteration, an image is shown with the weights produced, allowing a visual evaluation of the effectiveness of the trained model.

The iterative values used to test the different model configurations are:

Hyperparameter	Values
Optimizers	SGD, Adadelta, Adagrad, Adam, Adamax, FTRL, Nadam, RMS, Prop.
Activation Functions	Relu, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus, Softsign, Tanh, Selu, Elu, Exponential
Learning Rate	0.00001, 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1
Filters in Each Block	2, 4, 8

Table 4.2.2: Hyper parameters and their values

The training of each hyperparameter shows accuracy and loss metrics, as well as a visual representation of the weights 4.2.9.

Figure 4.2.9: Training Result

The hyperparameters that best fit the expected result after iteration and training with multiple models using the pre-defined values 4.2.2, are:

Hyperparameter	Final Value
Optimizer	SGD
Activation Function	Relu
Learning Rate	0.01
Filters in Each Block	4

Table 4.2.3: Hyper parameters and their values

The final model, with the chosen hyperparameters 4.2.3, presents a final result as follows 4.2.10, and this final model presents a tumor identification as shown in 4.2.11.

Figure 4.2.10: Final Training Result

Figure 4.2.11: Final Training Result (Visualization)

In order to generate the resulting image of the tumor, using a brain model, the previously trained model is used, which generates a resulting binarized image, where 0 is non-tumor tissue, and 1 is tumor tissue, as evidenced above 4.2.11. We relate this image as the generalized tumor section, which is usually divided into layers PVT, CTV and GTV, but this is outside the scope of this work and perhaps we could discuss it as a future work. Moreover, the same process is done for all the resulting layers of the entered model, thus obtaining various sections of the tumor 4.2.12.

Figure 4.2.12: Tumour Slices generation Using Predictions

Finally, all the slices generated from the predictions obtained with the trained model 4.2.12,

therefore, all the slices generated from the predictions obtained with the trained model are placed one on top of the other, and their spaces are completed by generating voxels in each section where the image is 1 (Tumor Tissue), which recreates the tumor region in 3D. Below is the 3D model of the brain (blue) and the 3D space of the tumor predicted with the neural network (orange) 4.2.13.

Figure 4.2.13: Final Voxels of the Tumour

Using the previously calculated matrix, the tumor volume is calculated using the number of tumor pixels found. To do this, the average brain size is defined, which is approximately:

- **Length:** 17 cm
- **Width:** 14 cm
- **Height:** 13 cm

This means that having a resolution of 224x224 pixels and 13 layers, and in the images used, approximately 70% of the length and 55% of the width of each image contain the brain, and the total layers used show the total height of the brain, in total, the brain of each slice measures:

- **Length:** $224\text{px} \times 70\% = 157\text{px}$
- **Width:** $224\text{px} \times 55\% = 123\text{px}$

- **Height:** 13px x 100% = 13px

Then, taking into account the average size of a brain, and the measurement of the brain in the images used in the model in pixels, the size in cm of each pixel can be calculated.

- **Length:** 17 cm / 157px = 0.108 cm/pixel
- **Width:** 14 cm / 123px = 0.114 cm/pixel
- **Height:** 13 cm / 13px = 1 cm/pixel

Therefore, the physical volume of each voxel is:

$$V_{\text{voxel}} = 0.108 \text{ cm} \times 0.114 \text{ cm} \times 1.0 \text{ cm} = 0.0123 \text{ cm}^3 \quad (4.1)$$

Knowing the total number of tumor pixels detected (N), the total tumor volume V_{tumor} is calculated as:

$$V_{\text{tumor}} = N \times V_{\text{voxel}} \quad (4.2)$$

In this case, with $N=2200$, the tumor volume was estimated to be [27.06 cm³], the tumor volume was estimated to be 27.06 cm³. This value is within the typical clinical range for brain tumors treated with radiotherapy or proton therapy. In clinical practice, an brain tumor volume of 27.06 cm³ corresponds to a moderate-sized tumor, consistent with intermediate-grade gliomas or large benign tumors such as meningiomas. Assuming approximate spherical symmetry, this volume corresponds to an effective diameter of approximately 3.7 cm, consistent with typical targets for proton therapy planning. This is important because it could section the PTV, CTV, or GTV layers; this also helps with radiotherapy planning.

4.2.4 Monte Carlo Simulation and Hybrid System

Monte Carlo simulation is a fundamental tool to model the interaction of radiation with biological tissue. I will use the ROOT framework together with Geant4 to evaluate the radiation dose distribution in a segmented three-dimensional model of a brain tumor. The methodology used consists of the generation of the voxelized matrix from the convolutional neural network (CNN), the conversion of the matrix to a geometric structure in ROOT and the Monte Carlo simulation

with Geant4 for the dose calculation. The tumor segmentation from medical images with the CNN generates a three-dimensional matrix in which each voxel represents a volume in space with a binary value: 1 for tumor tissue and 0 for healthy tissue. This matrix will be stored in HDF5 format and processed in ROOT for the construction of the geometry. The h5py library in Python will be used for the efficient manipulation of the HDF5 file, allowing the structured reading and writing of large volumes of data. In addition, a preprocessing with NumPy will be performed to correct possible artifacts and ensure the proper spatial alignment of the data.

For Monte Carlo simulation, the voxelized matrix must be converted into a ROOT-compatible geometric structure that will be used using ROOT's TGeo library, which allows the creation and manipulation of complex geometries, to model each voxel of the tumor as an individual volume within a larger-scale container representing the surrounding tissue. The voxelized matrix is loaded from the HDF5 file and the voxels corresponding to tumor tissue are identified, modeling them as independent volumes with dimensions proportional to the voxel size in the medical image. Each tumor voxel is assigned to a simulated biological material in ROOT and positioned within the mother volume using spatial transformations that preserve the organization of the segmented image. Subsequently, the physical properties of the materials involved are defined, including their density and attenuation coefficients, all of these data will be used from the NIST materials databases that are implemented in Geant4 to ensure an accurate simulation of the interaction of radiation with biological tissues by building the geometry in ROOT, the ionizing radiation interaction is simulated using Geant4. In Geant4, a primary event generator is defined by the G4ParticleGun class, which emits particles from an external source into the tumor volume. In conventional photonic radiotherapy, typical photon energies are around 1.25 MeV (e.g., from cobalt-60 sources). Then, in this study, we focused on advanced treatment modalities, specifically proton therapy, where protons are used instead of photons. For proton therapy, proton energies between 70 MeV and 250 MeV are typically used, depending on tumor depth. In this simulation, we selected a proton energy of 150 MeV, as this is the average energy used clinically to reach intermediate depths of 10 to 15 cm in human tissue, which correspond to typical locations of brain tumors. This energy choice ensures adequate penetration depth while preserving the Bragg peak properties of protons for highly localized dose delivery. In Geant4, the physical processes of electromagnetic interaction are modeled using the

G4EmStandardPhysics class, including the photoelectric effect, Compton scattering and pair production, allowing a detailed calculation of the energy deposited in each tumor voxel. To improve the accuracy of the dose calculation, particle tracking algorithms with G4Track and variance reduction techniques such as Russian Roulette and Splitting are implemented. Finally, the absorbed dose in each voxel is recorded using the G4Step class, generating a three-dimensional dose distribution map that can be analyzed to optimize radiotherapy treatment planning. This allows for more precise dose delivery and minimizes the impact on adjacent healthy tissue. This approach enables quantitative assessment of treatment effectiveness and suggests possible adjustments in radiotherapy parameters to improve clinical outcomes.

Figure 4.2.14: Tumor geometry

Let's describe it step by step. To create the hybrid system, I first need to connect the CNN and the MCS (Geant4), which includes the data format and how to do it. First, I load a voxel array from an HDF5 file and create a 3D representation of the tumor using ROOT. To do this, I open the HDF5 file, which contains the voxel array data, and extract the dimensions from the dataset. This is crucial for defining the size of the volume that will contain the geometry in ROOT. The code creates a geometry manager (TGeoManager), which defines a voxel material representing the biological tissue. This material is used to create a medium in which the voxels will be placed. Next, a mother volume is created that acts as a container for all the tumor voxels. The mother volume is a 3D cube sized appropriately based on the voxel array dimensions and the size of each voxel. The voxel array is then traversed, and for each voxel with a value of 1 (indicating it belongs to the tumor), an individual volume is created in ROOT. Each voxel is positioned in 3D space within the original volume using the corresponding coordinates. The tumor voxels are colored red for easy

visualization. Finally, the geometry is closed and displayed in an OpenGL window using the Draw function, allowing the generated 3D structure to be observed. The entire workflow can be described as: first, reading the voxel data from the HDF5 file; then, creating a 3D geometry with ROOT; then, positioning the voxels within a containing volume; and finally, visualizing the result. This 3D representation is crucial for simulating the tumor and analyzing dose distribution in radiotherapy simulations. The image could show the tumor represented by a collection of small cubes (voxels) colored red within an original volume, as can be seen in the figure4.2.14. This would highlight the tumor structure in 3D space, allowing us to understand how voxels are displayed and positioned in the context of the simulation.

At the same time, take the CSV file containing information about the voxels of a tumor and convert it into a ROOT file structured in a ROOT tree (TTree). The CSV file, which I will call Final Voxel.csv, contains columns with the three-dimensional coordinates of each voxel (x, y, z) and its corresponding value, which could represent, for example, the intensity of a tissue or the voxel's belonging to the tumor or the background. The process begins by reading the CSV file using the pandas library, which converts the file into a DataFrame, allowing easy manipulation of the rows and columns of the file. Once the data is loaded, the code creates a ROOT file named Final Voxel.root and a ROOT tree (TTree) called voxel tree. This tree is a hierarchical data structure that will store the voxel data efficiently. To organize the data in the tree, branches are defined that correspond to the x, y, and z coordinates of the voxels and their values (values). For each of these branches, a variable is created to store the data, and C++ vectors of type std.vector are used to dynamically manage the coordinate values and the voxel value. Upon completion, the code prints a message indicating that the conversion process was successful and that the ROOT file has been saved correctly. The result is a ROOT file containing the voxel data, ready to be used in Monte Carlo simulations, such as those performed in radiotherapy research, where working with large volumes of spatial and intensity data is essential as shown in the figure 4.2.15.

Figure 4.2.15: CNN to MCS (Geant4)

From here, I will use all of the above to begin the Monte Carlo simulation, which will be performed using Geant4. To do this, I will define the treatment from the beginning, considering the energy levels, the particles, and the types of interactions that depend on them. In this case, I will focus on proton radiotherapy to optimize the dose to a brain tumor.

Monte Carlo simulation is a fundamental tool in medical physics, especially for modeling the interaction of particles with matter. Its main advantage lies in its ability to accurately replicate the stochastic processes involved in particle propagation through different materials, such as human tissue. In the field of radiotherapy, this type of simulation is crucial for estimating dose distribution in the patient, optimizing treatments, and minimizing exposure to healthy tissue. This project implements a Monte Carlo simulation to study the interaction of 150 MeV protons with a brain tumor. The simulation is developed with Geant4, developed at CERN as an extension of ROOT, an open-source platform widely used in high-energy physics, astrophysics, and medical physics, among many other fields. Geant4 accurately models the interaction of charged particles with tissues and calculates the energy deposited in the tumor, essential for efficient proton radiotherapy.

Proton radiation therapy is an advanced cancer treatment modality that uses proton beams instead of photons or electrons. Its main advantage is the Bragg curve, which allows most of the proton's energy to be deposited in the tumor, minimizing damage to adjacent healthy tissue. This will be discussed in chapter 5, where physical modeling is described. Simulating this process is crucial for understanding dose distribution and improving treatment efficacy. The structure of the simulation developed in Geant4 is described below. The simulation is organized into several modules, each with a specific purpose: defining the geometry, the initial conditions of the protons (energies), the physical models used (types of interactions), and the energy deposited in the tumor. These modules are described in the following scripts, which are in Tables 4.2.4, 4.2.5 and 4.2.6.

File	Function	Description
Main.cc	Simulation setup and initialization.	Initializes Geant4 and its components, defines the geometry through DetectorConstruction, sets up the physical models with PhysicsList, specifies the proton source with PrimaryGeneratorAction, and manages the user interface.
DetectorConstruction.cc	Geometry and environment material definition.	Defines the geometry of the tumor and the materials of the environment, specifying a world volume, the tumor as a 10mm x 10mm x 10mm volume with biological tissue properties, and materials like water or soft tissue.
PrimaryGeneratorAction.cc	Proton source definition and propagation.	Defines the particle source: 150 MeV protons, with initial position (0, 0, -100 mm) and propagation along the Z-axis.
PhysicsList.cc	Physical models definition for the simulation.	Defines the physical models of the simulation: electromagnetic processes (ionization, Coulomb scattering), hadronic processes (inelastic collisions), and secondary particle production.
TumorSensitiveDetector.cc	Energy deposition recording and interaction position.	Records the energy deposited by protons in the tumor and the position of each interaction, saving the results in energy_deposition.txt.
EventAction.cc	Absorbed dose calculation in Gray (Gy).	Calculates the absorbed dose in Gray (Gy), dividing the total deposited energy by the tumor mass.
ActionInitialization.cc	Initialization of actions for the simulation.	Initializes the main actions for the simulation, such as event initialization and creation of corresponding actions.
RunAction.cc	Management of actions at the 'run' level and result storage.	Manages actions at the 'run' level, such as statistical initialization and storing results for each run.
SteppingAction.cc	Management of actions during each step of the particles.	Manages actions during each step of the particles, allowing detailed analysis like energy deposition at each step or trajectory tracking.

Table 4.2.4: File Descriptions and their Functions

File	Function	Description
ActionInitialization.hh	Declaration of initial simulation actions.	Defines the classes and functions necessary to initialize the main actions for the simulation, such as event creation and configuration of corresponding actions.
DetectorConstruction.hh	Declaration of geometry and environment materials.	Defines the classes and methods to set up the geometry and materials for the simulation environment, including the tumor and surrounding materials.
PrimaryGeneratorAction.hh	Declaration of proton source and propagation.	Defines the classes needed for creating and propagating 150 MeV protons, specifying the source and direction of propagation in the simulation.
PhysicsList.hh	Declaration of physical models for the simulation.	Defines the classes that include the necessary physical models for the simulation, such as electromagnetic and hadronic processes.
TumorSensitiveDetector.hh	Declaration of detector sensitivity and energy recording.	Declares the necessary classes for recording energy deposition in the tumor and the position of each interaction during the simulation.
EventAction.hh	Declaration of actions for absorbed dose calculation.	Defines the classes for calculating the absorbed dose in Gray (Gy), using the deposited energy and tumor mass.
RunAction.hh	Declaration of actions at the 'run' level.	Defines the classes that manage actions at the "run" level, such as statistical initialization and results collection.
SteppingAction.hh	Declaration of actions during each particle step.	Declares the classes for managing each particle step, such as recording energy deposition and tracking trajectories.

Table 4.2.5: File Actions

File	Function	Description
run.mac	Run the simulation in batch mode and set execution parameters.	The run.mac file contains commands to execute the simulation in batch mode. It defines parameters such as running the simulation and required scripts.
vis.mac	Configure visualization options and the graphical interface.	The vis.mac file configures the simulation's visualization options, specifying how events, geometry, and other graphical aspects should be displayed during the simulation.
CMakeLists.txt	Set up the project build process with CMake.	The CMakeLists.txt file contains the necessary instructions to compile and link the project using CMake, specifying dependencies and required directories.

Table 4.2.6: Overview of Simulation Configuration Files

Chapter 5: Results and Analysis.

5.1 Results

The development of this project has allowed the integration of advanced machine learning techniques and Monte Carlo simulations with Geant4 to improve dosimetry in proton radiotherapy treatments. The combination of these tools has enabled a detailed evaluation of the dose distribution within the tumor volume, thus optimizing treatment planning. To achieve this, a process of image segmentation, tumor voxelization, and radiotherapy simulation was followed, which approximates an optimal dose distribution model for the tumor, increasing the amount of energy deposited on tumor tissue and reducing the energy in healthy tissue.

The implementation phase of the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was key in brain tumor segmentation, providing highly accurate voxelized geometry that was subsequently incorporated into the Monte Carlo simulation. This approach made it possible to accurately represent the patient's anatomy, identify the tumor site, and subsequently simulate proton transport through the tissue, analyzing energy deposition within the tumor.

The amount of data used for training the model (CNN) is divided into training data, validation data, and test data. Training and validation data are used to train the model and change the weights of the neurons to improve the prediction result. Test data is used to check the veracity of the previously trained model and calculate the accuracy and loss of the model. The amount of data used for each situation is shown below 5.1.1.

Figure 5.1.1: Train/Test Images Amount of CNN Model

The images obtained with the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) are separated into three steps. First, brain images are filtered and processed, and image enhancement methods are applied to visualize the tumor section with higher quality 5.1.2, then the processed images are entered into the previously trained model, which produces as a result images that represent the brain approximation visualized from the model 5.1.3, and a resulting image of the final tumor section 5.1.4.

Figure 5.1.2: Original image (Left) and Preprocessed image (Right)

Figure 5.1.3: Model Aproximations

Figure 5.1.4: Final Model Result

This process allows for the approximate location of the tumor in the patient’s brain, which allows for identifying the region where the greatest amount of protons should be irradiated using radiotherapy. Below 5.1.5, are various brain images and their respective tumor sections identified using the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model.

Figure 5.1.5: Model results of different input images

The identification process is performed for all layers (cross-sections) of the complete brain model, identifying the tumor section of each layer, and then stacking the images to generate a voxelized 3D model 5.1.6.

Figure 5.1.6: Tumour final 3D model, Brain (Blue) - Tumour (Orange)

One of the main findings of the study is the validation of the Bragg Peak effect 5.1.7 in proton radiotherapy, which shows a pronounced curve just before the proton stops when it reaches the tumor site, thereby increasing the radiation dose to the tissue being treated and decreasing it to healthy tissue.

Figure 5.1.7: Proximity to the tumor [mm] vs Radiation Dose [%]

This shows 5.1.7 that as the tumor approaches, the dose percentage gradually decreases as it travels through the brain. Then, when it reaches the point where the dose is expected to be deposited (0mm proximity to the tumor), it increases by approximately 20%, causing the tumor to receive the greatest amount of dose, while the remaining healthy tissue receives a smaller amount.

As expected, the majority of the energy deposited occurs in the tumor region, thus minimizing exposure to surrounding healthy tissue. The simulation has allowed quantification of the total energy deposited (MeV) 5.1.8 5.1.9, and the position of the interaction event, providing key information for improving the personalization of radiotherapy treatments.

Figure 5.1.8: Map of the dose deposited in the tumor (2D) [10.000 particles simulated]

Figure 5.1.9: Map of the dose deposited in the tumor (3D) [10.000 particles simulated]

The previous images 5.1.8 5.1.9, show how the energy dose counted in MeV, using a 50000 simulated events, is kept at very low percentages until reaching the tumor (approximately between -10 and 10mm in both the x and y axes), which receives the highest amount of dose, avoiding over-exposure of healthy tissues to high doses. In figure 2D 5.1.8, the exposure is shown only on the x and y axes, and in figure 3D 5.1.9, the exposure is shown on all three axes.

The results obtained have demonstrated that the proposed methodology can be applied in clinical settings to improve dose delivery precision and reduce toxicity in critical organs. Furthermore, the detailed analysis of energy distribution has identified opportunities for optimization in treatment planning through proton energy modulation and radiation beam configuration.

5.2 Limitations and Challenges

Despite the achievements, this study has certain limitations. Monte Carlo simulation, although highly accurate, is computationally expensive, limiting the number of events that can be simulated in a reasonable timeframe. In clinical applications, integrating these models with computational optimization techniques, for example the GPU acceleration 5.2.1 or hybrid techniques could improve performance without compromising accuracy, as demonstrated by the comparative study between the performance of processors and GPUs in calculating large volumes of data and graphic information (Gaxiola and Tapia 2011).

Figure 5.2.1: Processor Performance Comparison (CPU vs GPU)

Another aspect to consider is the CNN model's sensitivity to the quality of the input data. While tumor segmentation was accurate in most cases, small variations in image quality can affect the neural network's performance, as shown below 5.2.2. Future versions could incorporate new data augmentation and transfer learning techniques to improve the model's robustness.

Figure 5.2.2: Comparison between a clean image and a noisy image, Clean (Left) - Noisy (Right)

Furthermore, the voxelized representation of the tumor, although detailed, can benefit from advanced image reconstruction techniques to improve interpolation between regions of interest. The implementation of artificial intelligence-based models for medical image reconstruction could be a future line of research to optimize segmentation quality.

Chapter 6: Discussion and Future Work

Based on the results obtained, it can be verified how effectively the use of radiotherapy allows reaching the section of the tumor by increasing the dose it receives, and decreasing the dose received by healthy tissue, although in the same way, healthy tissue continues to receive a certain amount of radiotherapy dose, which although less, can affect it to a greater or lesser extent. This long-term damage could be measured to verify the viability of the treatment on a patient. On the other hand, it is very important to be able to detect the location of the tumor as precisely as possible, since if the region to be treated is not detected correctly, healthy tissue that has been taken as a tumor can be affected when it really was not, this is why special emphasis and attention must be placed on detection using the neural network, and to be able to verify that effectively the tumor section defined by the model is the region of the tumor that is really going to be treated. So, even with a powerful tool like a neural detection network, it's essential to have expert human support to verify the results obtained and the validity of the area being treated, to avoid false treatments and overdosing in untreatable areas or healthy tissue.

This study has demonstrated that the combination of convolutional neural networks and Monte Carlo simulations allows for more precise and efficient planning of proton radiotherapy. The developed methodology allowed for automatic tumor segmentation, modeling its voxelized geometry in Geant4, and simulating proton interaction to determine dose distribution with high accuracy. The results obtained validate the use of proton radiotherapy as an effective and precise technique, maximizing dose to the tumor region while minimizing damage to healthy tissue. Furthermore, the implementation of artificial intelligence-based tools represents a major advance in the automation and personalization of cancer treatments.

With this in mind, the greatest amount of resources should be invested in network training and subsequent validation, taking into account the large load that training a network of this robustness requires. It must also be taken into account that the quality of the input image considerably affects its output, which can generate other unforeseen errors.

Based on this, various changes can be developed and implemented that can improve not only the detection of the tumor region, but also improve irradiation to optimize the amount of energy absorbed

by the tissue to be treated, and minimize the energy absorbed by healthy tissue as much as possible. If we wanted to improve the neural network, we could explore more advanced architectures such as U-Net, V-Net, or Transformers to improve tumor segmentation, implementing transfer learning to improve model performance on more diverse clinical data and performing uncertainty analysis to assess the model's robustness across different image types. Then, with a better location of the sector to be treated, the Monte Carlo simulation can be improved and optimized. implementing variance reduction strategies to improve simulation efficiency without losing accuracy, exploring the use of GPU acceleration with libraries such as CUDA or OpenCL to increase the number of simulated events in less time, and integrate dose optimization models to personalize radiotherapy treatments in real time.

In addition to the technical and technological improvements described above, the results can also be improved by using different techniques such as comparing the results of the simulations obtained with real-world patient clinical data to validate the model's accuracy, collaborate with medical institutions to apply the model to personalized treatment planning and incorporate dosimetric assessment methods based on experimental measurements to validate the accuracy of the simulated dose distribution. To achieve this, it is important to be able to integrate the model with clinical software, it can be developed a graphical interface that allows physicians to interactively view simulation results, integrate the tool with treatment planning systems (TPS) used in hospitals, and incorporate artificial intelligence models to predict and optimize tumor response to radiation.

In the future, the integration of computational optimization techniques, validation with real clinical data, and GPU acceleration will further improve model performance and its applicability in clinical settings. This work lays the foundation for the development of advanced computational tools in the field of radiation oncology, with the potential to significantly improve cancer treatment outcomes.

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